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“STUDY ON VARIOUS PARAMETERS FORTIFIED PANEER SPREAD”

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ABSTRACT

Objective-The objectives of the present study is to increase the shelf life of paneer spread by adding clove extract as additive at different concentrations. Methods- The probiotic bacteria have been isolated from the milk and curd for the development of fortified paneer spread. The isolates were grown on MRS (de Man, Rogosa and Sharpe) media which are subsequently morphologically and biochemically characterized. Fortified Paneer spread was prepared by modified conventional method which includes heat coagulation, addition of acid coagulant and probiotic bacteria, grinding pressing and hooping. At the end of the procedure paneer spread was prepared by optimizing salt and moisture content. The shelf life of paneer spread can be improved by incorporation of clove extract at specific level was optimized for final paneer spread. Result –Modified paneer spreads sample were prepared that were fortified with *Bifidobacterium spp.* Clove extract was added to increase the shelf life and sensory characteristics of the paneer spread. Conclusion -The study found that clove extract increases the shelf life of the paneer spread significantly. The attempts has been made to prepare paneer spread having better nutritional value and shelf life of paneer based spreads which is a better alternative for cheese and butter spreads in the market.

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INTRODUCTION

Probiotic is a Greek word 'pro bios' which means 'for life' opposed to antibiotic which means 'against life' [1]. The concept of probiotics has introduced several beneficial physiological effects i.e. good health along with negligible adverse effects. Probiotics are the living microorganisms that benefit the host when taken up in adequate amount, by improving its intestinal microbial balance and have shown to change the composition of colonic microbiota [2].

In the past two decades usage of probiotic is increasing in dairy products like cheese, butter, yoghurts and fermented milks and paneer. Butter and cheese Spreads, both are the forms of dairy products that can be easily consumed by large population in the world. Butter is a source of high fat which is responsible for coronary heart diseases hence most of the health conscious consumers avoid its consumption [3]. The factors like high cost of butter along with its high-saturated fatty acids, cholesterol level, calorific value and poor spreadability at room temperature limits its application [4]. So people are searching for the alternative of cheese which has merits over primary cheese. Paneer is a variety of soft cheese prepared by acid and heat coagulation of milk [5,6]. It is a non-fermentative, non-renneted, non-melting and unripened type of cheese containing high moisture content (50-60%) [7] and it should not exceed up to 70% and fat content should not be more than 50% of the dry matter according to PFA [8].

The quality of paneer depends on the quality of milk from which it is produced. The shorter shelf life of paneer is considered to be a biggest hurdle in its production at commercial level. Paneer can be stored for only 6 days at 10 C without much deterioration in its quality [9, 10]. The study has been conducted for 12 spices that were tested, and found that clove and clove oil having antimicrobial activity [11].

All these key factors have lead to plan an investigation with the objectives; to study the effect of *bifidobacterium sp.* on the textural and sensory properties of paneer and to increase the shelf life of paneer by adding clove extract at different temperatures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Isolation of probiotic bacteria

For the development of fortified paneer spread the probiotic bacteria has been isolated from the milk and curd.

Microscopic characterization of isolates

Identification of isolates was performed by microscopic tests including Gram staining and motility test.

Biochemical characterization of isolates

The biochemical tests of isolates includes starch hydrolysis, citrate utilization test, catalase test, starch, gelatin and casein hydrolysis test, triple sugar iron test, Indole production Methyl- Red & Vogues- Proskauer Test , Arginine Hydrolysis Test ,and carbohydrate fermentation test.

Selection of potential probiotics

Probiotic bacterial cultures must be capable of surviving and growing in the intestine and maintaining their viability and activity. Potential probiotic bacteria have been selected on the basis of following characteristics.

Acid tolerance

The tolerance of isolates to acids was evaluated in MRS containing 3% bromocresol purple with pH 1, 2 and 3 by using 0.1 N HCl with 1 ml of overnight probiotic culture, and then incubated an-aerobically for 24-hour at 37°C followed by change of the color from purple to yellow [12].

Bile tolerance

MRS broth containing 3% bromocresol purple which was supplemented with 0.3% bile salts with 1 ml overnight culture incubated an-aerobically at 37°C for 2-4 days, followed by change of the color from purple to yellow [13].

Growth at Different Temperatures

MRS containing 3% bromocresol purple indicator were incubated with overnight culture for 7 days at 10°C, 15°C, and 45°C and cells growth at different temperatures was observed by the change of the cultures, from purple to yellow [14].

Growth at Different NaCl Concentrations

MRS medium containing 3% bromocresol purple with two different concentrations of NaCl - 4% and 6.5% with 1% overnight cultures of isolates and then incubated an-aerobically at 37°C for 7 days [14].

Preparation of paneer

Fortified Paneer was prepared as per modified method (Bhattacharya et al., 1971). The standardized milk was heated to 90°C (No holding) in a stainless steel vessel and cooled up to 70°C. Followed by adding hot solution (70°C) of one percent citric acid and *bifidobacterium* with vigorous agitation initially and gentle stirring later till clear whey was separated out. Then the coagulum was allowed to settle down for 5 minutes. Fortified Paneer samples and there components are described in table I.

Optimization of concentration of the coagulant

Various concentration of the citric acid solution ranging from 1% - 4% was used for the optimization of concentration of the coagulant. 2% citric acid solution was found to be optimum concentration for a paneer with desired quality characteristics.

Optimization of the grinding duration

Paneer curd was grinded for different durations ranging from 1, 2, 4 and 6 minutes to optimize the grinding time. Two minutes grinding time was found to be optimum for preparing paneer spread.

Incorporation of herbs at different concentration in paneer spread

Clove extract are added at the rate of 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5 % per kg of milk during the preparation of paneer spread.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Colony morphology of isolated probiotic bacteria on MRS agar and *bifidobacterium* selective media:

Total 6 microbial isolates (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5 and C6) were obtained, from milk and yogurt. Gram staining and catalase test was performed for these isolates; all isolates were Gram positive, rod and Y-shaped as shown in figure 1 and table II. Colonies were appeared creamy white in color, circular in shape, convex elevated and smooth rough textured.

Biochemical Characterization

Biochemical test was done for all 6 microbial isolates. Results of biochemical test were mentioned in table III. Careful study of biochemical characterization as shown in table-III revealed that all isolates were not able to utilize casein, citrate, gelatin and able to ferment sugars used for carbohydrate fermentation test shown in table IV.

Acid tolerance and Bile salt tolerance

It was observed that out of 6 isolates, 3 were able to grow in pH 2 as well as pH 3. The results indicate that the isolates obtained show satisfactory results under the criteria for probiotic microorganisms. Effect of different physiological condition on growth of probiotic microorganisms observed in table-V.

Effect of various concentration of citric acid solution on the quality of paneer spread

Textural and organoleptic properties of the paneer spread were observed for the effect of different concentrations of citric acid solution that was recorded in table VI. Citric acid concentration of 1% was found to produce spreadable product.

Effect of various grinding duration (minutes) on the quality of paneer spread

The paneer curd was subjected for different durations of grinding such that a spreadable product can be obtained. Textural and organoleptic characteristics were observed for the effect of grinding duration on the quality of paneer spread is presented in the table-VII. Grinding duration of 2 minutes was found to produce a uniform texture and easily spreadable product.

Effect of clove extract on the sensory characteristics of paneer spread

Clove extract was incorporated at various levels to study quality of paneer spread is presented in the Table-VIII.

Body and texture:

The color and appearance scores recorded for P4 was highest (22.90) and lowest for the sample P1 (20.56). It has been observed that increased concentration of clove extract in a paneer sample increases the body and texture scores.

Color and appearance:

The highest were recorded to be 13.14 for P4. Whereas, the lowest score of 12.03 was awarded to control. On other hand, P1 had been given score of 12.15. The body and texture scores of P4 were significantly higher than control as well as other treated samples.

Overall acceptability:

Maximum Overall acceptability score was recorded for the paneer spread sample P4 (92.22). There is no significant difference between the spread samples of control (87.59) and P1 (87.88).

Effect of clove extract on the shelf life of the paneer spread

Sensory characteristics

Effect of clove extract was measured at hedonic scale score system for paneer spread and presented in the table-IX. The highest shelf life of paneer spread sample P2 was recorded at 4°C and 8°C as compared to other spread samples. Whereas paneer spread sample P4 displayed highest shelf life (15 days) at 30°C.

Tables and Figures.

Table I: Fortified Paneer samples and there components.

S. No.	Fortified Paneer	Composition
1.	Paneer 1	Standardized milk + Coagulants
2.	Paneer 2	Standardized milk+ Coagulant+ Probiotic bacteria + clove extract

Table-II: Morphological Identification and Gram staining of Isolates.

S. No.	Isolates from milk and yogurt	Gram staining (In duplicates)	Shape
1.	C 1	+	Rod shape
2.	C 2	+	Rod Shaped, bifurcated Y form
3.	C 3	+	Rod Shaped, bifurcated Y form
4.	C 4	-	Rod shape
5.	C 5	+	Rod Shaped, bifurcated Y form
6.	C 6	+	Rod Shaped, bifurcated Y form

Table-III: Biochemical tests for isolates.

S. No.	Isolates from food sample	Catalase	Indole	Gelatin	Casein	Citrate	MR	VP	Starch	Arginine	TSI		
											GP	H ₂ S	SF
1	CS 1	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+
2	CS 3	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+
3	CS 6	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+

Table-IV: Test for Carbohydrate fermentation.

S. No.	Isolates from dairy product	Carbohydrates						
		Glucose	Sucrose	Maltose	Fructose	Lactose	Galactose	Sorbitol
1	CS 1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	CS 3	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3	CS 6	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Table-V: Effect of different physiological condition on growth of probiotic microorganisms.

4S. No.	Sample	Growth at			NaCl		pH			0.3% bile salt
		10°C	15°C	45°C	2%	6.5%	1	2	3	
1	A 1	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
2	A 3	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
3	A 6	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+

Table-VI: Effect of concentration of citric acid solution on the quality characteristics of paneer spread.

Sensory attributes	Perfect score [15]	Concentration of Citric acid solution (%)			
		1.0%	2.0%	3.0%	4.0%
Colour and appearance	15	7.50	7.53	7.51	7.52
Body and Texture	35	29.53	25.89	23.02	20.49
Overall acceptability	100	86.19	82.89	82.72	80.10

Table-VII: Effect of grinding duration on the quality of paneer spread.

	Grinding duration (minutes)				
	0	1	2	4	6
Colour and appearance	Curdy	Uneven, slightly glossy	Smooth and glossy	Slightly creamy	Separation of cream
Body and Texture	Curdy, granular	Granular	Smooth	Lumps of cream	Clumpy
Flavor	Uneven salty	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
Overall acceptability	Non acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Non acceptable	Non acceptable

Table-VIII: Effect of clove extract on the sensory characteristics of paneer spread.

Sensory attributes	Concentration of Clove extract (%)				
	0 %	0.5%	1.0%	1.5%	2.0%
	Control	P1	P2	P3	P4
Body and Texture	21.34	20.56	22.34	22.42	22.90
Colour and appearance	12.03	12.15	12.19	13.09	13.14
Overall acceptability	87.59	87.88	90.33	92.12	92.22

Where, P1 = Paneer spread sample 1, P2 = Paneer spread sample 2, P3 = Paneer spread sample 3, P4 = Paneer spread sample 4

Table-IX: Effect of clove extract on the shelf life (in days) of paneer spread.

Temperature (°C)	Concentration of clove extract (%)				
	0 %	0.5%	1.0%	1.5%	2.0%
	Control	P1	P2	P3	P4
4°C	4 days	15 days	20 days	18 days	17 days
8°C	4 days	12 days	16 days	15 days	12 days
30°C	2 days	10 days	12 days	13 days	15 days

Figure I: Morphological Identification of isolates; (a) & (b) Isolated *lactobacillus* spp., (c) & (d) Isolated *bifidobacterium* spp. (e) Gram staining of *lactobacillus* spp. (f) Gram staining of *bifidobacterium* spp.

CONCLUSION

The increasing demand for the traditional dairy products has lead to more research in this area and increase the nutritional and functional quality of these products. Paneer is one of the common indian dairy products whose beneficial value is comparatively better than dairy products like cheese and butter. Therefore, in this study various type of paneer-based spreads have been prepared by fortifying them with probiotics species was a value added factor. Paneer spread sample P2 exhibited best result after addition of 1% clove concentration at 4 °C. This study may suggest the 1% clove concentration may be used as preservatives for enhancement of shelf life of paneer spread. This is preliminary study to prepare paneer spread having better shelf life which will be further used at commercial scale. Paneer spread is improved by incorporation of various flavor enhancers at specific level. There is a great scope for the dairy sector in India to explore this newly developed paneer based spreads as a better alternative for cheese and butter spreads in the market. Further research could be extended to areas of packaging of the paneer spread so that the product can be easily marketed and stored at low temperature.

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